

An Alternative for Soy: Turning Grass Into Feed

A small-scale biorefinery **converts freshly harvested grass into different products** by shredding and pressing the grass.

Press Cake

Benefits:

- Reduce costs
- Saves emissions
- Diversifies income

Grass Juice

Can be used as ...

...fibre feed for cattle.

...bio-based fertiliser.

...dried feed for monogastric animals.